

RES4CITY CASE STUDY #4

Sustainable Heating: Grenoble's Solutions for Heat Recovery from a Nearby Industry

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Executive Summary

Figure 9. Advance controls of storage and use of waste heat from a nearby industry – Graphical Abstract

This case study presents the heating network in Grenoble, including its stakeholders and the different power plants involved. The results show that among the three scenarios presented, the most realistic is the scenario with

25% wood pellets and 75% wood consumption. In fact, the construction of a new power plant is not useful since this plant would only operate half of the time foreseen.

Abstract

Because of its concern for eco-development and alpine environment, Grenoble has made energy transition and the development of renewable energies its priority and was named European Green Capital in 2022. The limited available space made dense public transport and heat networks more profitable and then earlier and more developed than elsewhere which provides us with many application cases of interest for the Renewable Energies System for Cities (RES4CITY). The Metropolitan

heat network of Grenoble provides heat, some others allow to provide also cold, to one or more consumers. In the case of Grenoble, all types of consumers are connected: hospitals, industries, services, public building, private dwellings, which covers most of the cases of use and interactions that can be thought about, this connection is called district heating. The energy feeding the network has been shifting progressively away from the original fossil fuels. Waste incineration heat retrieval was

first set up, then biomass was added, and now industrial heat recovery technologies are increasing the volume of renewable calories used. The goal of the lighthouse case study is to transfer to students the inspiration, action, and solutions, by showcasing how renewable and innovative technologies are integrated in the Grenoble metropolitan area. The proposed lighthouse case will provide a better understanding of such a system from three different points of view.

i) First, the technological aspect is presented in terms of design of the grid (sources, tubes and potential storages), operating and maintenance principles as well as the operation of the grid, its sources and eventual storages for short-term and long-term periods.

ii) Second, from the economic standpoint, the aim is to understand the optimal control of the available resources. On the one hand, the short-term economic benefits (related to

operation) of resources and grid optimization were analysed. On the other hand, over the long term, given the level of uncertainty over the decisions of many actors, such as connection of new customers or new sources, how the optimal planning of the energy resources potentially available in the local system can be carried out was explored. In this sense, we propose various technical-economic modelling scenarios for the complete decarbonization of the network.

iii) Third, heat networks connect many different categories of stakeholders: designers, builders, operators, customers, and users that are all needed but have different levels of understanding of the system and potentially opposite interests. The lighthouse case will improve their understanding of the system, its interest for a better environment, and their role in its development and governance.

Introduction

Just a while ago, on 30th March 2023, the European Union has sent a very strong signal for its energy policy, planning to double the share of renewable energies by 2030s in the energy mix of the 27 countries (EC,2023). Among other strategies, this acceleration from the current level (around 22%, Eurostat (2023) to 42.5 % of renewables in consumption will necessarily have to go

through the massive deployment of additional renewable heat sources, as a tool for the energy transition. In Europe, there is a diversity of heating sources for reasons related to the historical context, to the choices of energy policy or to the climatic conditions conditioning the amount of heat consumed. When the conditions are favourable, the heating systems¹ can have important benefits by using local renewable energies and by contributing to the energy transition of territories in the long term.

Problem to be addressed and its relevance.

District heating networks are now in operation in most of the major cities in France. In France, consumption for heat production (all modes combined) represents 741 TWh and the energy mix is mainly fossil, with 61% of the heat produced from natural gas, oil and coal. Only 21% of this heat comes from renewable and recovered energies. District heating networks make it

possible to provide 3.5% of national heat consumption. They have the advantage of providing energy mainly produced from renewable and recovered energies.

The city of Grenoble has made significant progress in sustainable development, especially in the energy sector. With a focus on research and development, the city has become a hub for innovation, particularly in the fields of energy, nanoelectronics, and biotechnology. In recent years, Grenoble has prioritized sustainable development, with a focus on reducing pollution and greenhouse gas emissions.

One major success story in this regard is the city's heating network, which spans 177 km and is 80% powered by renewable energy sources (Grenoble's Urban Heating, 2022). This makes it the second-largest heat network in France, and the city has been working for years to further decarbonize and

improve the network. Grenoble has set a goal of reducing its emissions by 80% over the next 30 years, and the success of its heating network has made it a model for other cities to follow. Overall, Grenoble's focus on sustainable development and its success in implementing renewable energy sources in its heating network make it an excellent model for other cities looking to reduce their carbon footprint and prioritize sustainability.

Challenges and expected benefits from the work

As part of the RES4CITY project, this lighthouse case study aims to gain a comprehensive understanding of the intricate heating network in Grenoble, including its stakeholders and the different power plants involved. Given that data collection is a crucial part of this work, one of the main challenges is the unavailability of easily accessible data, particularly regarding the heating network technologies and its stakeholders. The aim of this

study is to contribute to the development of the RES4CITY project and support the city of Grenoble in its ongoing efforts towards sustainable development. By providing detailed and convincing calculations related to the decarbonization of the heating network, this project aims to help policymakers and stakeholders make informed decisions that would benefit the environment and the local community. Furthermore, our work is intended to be widely disseminated, making it accessible to anyone who is interested in the topic of sustainable energy and heat networks. Additionally, sharing our findings and recommendations can be helpful for other cities and communities looking to implement similar measures, especially in the context of the global transition towards a low-carbon economy. Ultimately,

Literature review and gaps

There is a wide literature on urban heating networks, including academic research, textbooks, and different annual reports from related entities. There are currently 5 plants producing heat in Grenoble, 3 of them operating in cogeneration, but one has not been operating since 2012 (CCIAG, 2023). The impact of the construction of a new plant, BIOMAX, in Grenoble in different technical reports. Bureau Veritas Exploitation, Ingevalor and (2017) detail the environment of the selected site in Grenoble and explain all the analysis of the impact that this plant could have on its environment. It also details the way the parcel could have evolved without this project. All the dangers linked to the creation of this plant have also been studied and the exploitants have applied for the authorization to operate. This more technical document explains the operation of the plant, following every step of the process. It also details the

way this plant will become a part of the heat network, comparing the actual situation with the potential future situation with the plant. Rossi & Petit (2021) provide the elements to consider when it comes to CO2 computations of a heat network: the life-cycle analysis, the direct emissions and the emissions avoided thanks to the cogeneration. A study has been done to add more industrial heat recovery in the network, with the National Laboratory for Intense Magnetic Fields (LNCMI) (Hodencq, 2019). This laboratory works on magnets, and produces heat as a byproduct. Currently, they are using the Drac's River cold water to cool their process, so a connection to the heat network could be profitable to prevent the waste. But this heat source would be intermittent because it depends on the experiment schedule. An example of the expansion of the heat network to link all 100 university's

buildings have been studied, to reduce the CO2 emissions of the university, and to be less dependent on fossil fuels (L'université Grenoble Alpes (Uga) et al., 2021). The technologies of thermal energy storage for heat networks are presented by Martinelli (2018). A dynamic modelling and management of heat networks are proposed by Giraud (2016). Finally, a connection of waste heat sources located near or in dense urban areas to heat networks is studied by Chiche (2020).

Objective of the work

Our work aims to present an extended overview of the technologies, the stakeholders and the economic optimization of the heating network as stated in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Main objectives

This case study aims to answer the issue of what needs to be done to reach 100% of renewable and recovered energies in the heating network by 2033, by offering different possible options. Our methodological approach will be based on scenarios (incorporation of short-term uncertainties related to the operation issues and long-term uncertainties associated with changes in market prices or financing costs influencing investments). This question raises the issue of the primary energy sources used to produce heat, and the variable availability of some of these sources, such as wood or the city's waste.

Description of Case Study

The heating network in Grenoble is the second biggest heating network in France, and the heat delivered corresponds to 100,000 housing equivalents. It provides heat to the city's Hospital, its different museums, the university, the town hall, various sports centres and many private housings (Grenoble's Urban Heating, 2022). This heat network is owned by the Metropolis of Grenoble, and it is exploited by the CCIAG under a contract of public services delegation as stated in Figure 11.

The network consists of 178 km of pipes spread under the public road in 7 cities of the Agglomeration (Grenoble, Echirolles, Eybens, Gières, La Tronche, Le Pont-de-Claix and Saint-Martin-d'Hères). The heat is provided by 5 plants (Athamor, Biomax, Poterne, Villeneuve and Vaucanson, which doesn't produce anymore) and 1 unit of heat recovery. There is 1200 m³

of thermal storage located in the sites of 2 production units. These storages help to have better flexibility and to smooth the production during peak hours. All the power plants operate with the principle of incineration: the water of the network is heated thanks to the incineration of fuels. Amongst the five thermal units, three of them work in cogeneration, meaning they produce both electricity and heat.

Figure 11. Map of the Network - Source: (Grenoble’s Urban Heating, 2022)

As shown in Figure 12, the main fuels used are wood (35.2%), household waste (43.8%), coal (5.4%), fuel oil (0.2%), bone meal (1.0%) and natural gas (14.3%) for the year 2022 (Grenoble's Urban Heating, 2022). Due to the contract between Grenoble's metropolis and the CCIAG, the

wood sources must come from a radius of a maximum of 50 km, and at least 11% must come from sustainable sources. The "waste" wood comes from the department and a neighbouring department, as the town alone does not provide enough. The repartition of each source in the plants is presented in Table 5.

**Figure 12. Energy mix of the network - Source:
(Grenoble's Urban Heating, 2022)**

Table 5. Raw Materials for each plant - Source: (Grenoble's Urban Heating, 2022)

Heat production sites	Raw materials
Poterne (Cogeneration)	Wood (forestry chips)
	Wood (end-of-life packaging)
	Bone meal
	Natural gas
	Coal
Villeneuve	Wood (forestry chips)
	Wood (end-of-life packaging)
	Fuel oil
	Coal
Athamor (Cogeneration)	Fuel oil
	Natural gas
	Household garbage
Biomax (Cogeneration)	Wood (forestry chips)
	Wood (end-of-life packaging)
	Natural gas
Vaucanson	Heating oil
Solvay (Pont-de-claix)	plant activity (8MW) (hydrogen)
	plant activity (24MW) (hydrogen)

The heat recovery unit is located in the Chemical Platform of Le Pont-de-Claix, the project is Solcia, by Solvay and consists of heat exchanges in a year (Solvay, 2023). During summer, the power plant

Athamor produces too much heat from city waste, so Solvay consumes heat from the network for its industrial activities, which allows them to consume less natural gas.

During winter, Solvay produces its own heat for the industrial activities, and sells the waste heat to the network, which helps the CCIAG to have a reater flexibility during peak hours. Overall, 3.3% of the heat produced in 2022 came from industrial heat (Grenoble’s Urban Heating, 2022). The network uses 80.1% of

renewable and recovered sources. The project of the CCIAG is to reach 100% by 2033, see Figure 13 below. The BIOMAX plant is relatively new (2021) and only renewable sources, while some are older but have refurbishment projects, like Poterne, that plan to stop using coal by 2026, to replace it with renewable sources.

Figure 4 : MindMap of Grenoble’s heat network

- 1 Serve Grand’Place commercial area with 6°C cold water
- 2 Chemical platform of Pont-de-Claix ; Project Solcia by Solvay
in winter : supplies heat to the urban network sources : hydrogen and gas ; sales of waste heat by Solvay and reduction of consumption of fuel oil or gas by CCIAG and greater flexibility during peak hours
in summer : takes the heat from the work for its own business : reduction of gas consumption by Solvay and valorisation of the production surplus by CCIAG
- 3 Biomax : wood - thermal storage of 450m³ of overheated water to allow flexibility during peak hours
Athanor : household waste, fuel oil, gas - incineration plant, electricity : 54% of self-consumption
Poterne : wood, bone meal, gas, coal - incineration plant, project to stop coal use by 2026
Villeneuve : wood, fuel oil, coal - incineration plant, thermal storage during a day (750m³ at most)
Voucanson : fuel oil - incineration plant ; safety plant ; unused since 2012
- 4 4.3 millions of net total
Usage fee of 5.2 millions per year to Grenoble Metropolis
Concession of 15 years
- 5 Supply CCIAG with :
 - heating network and production sites
 - fuel, 80.1% of renewables and recovery energy (wood 40.2%, household waste 36.2%, coal 12.1%, fuel oil 5.9%, bone meal 1.4% and gas 0.8%)
 - wood platform Goncein (50% packaging wood at its end of life, 50% of forest wood)
 - forest managed sustainably (label PEFC, FSC,...) in the departement of Isère and Savoie.
- 6
 - 178km of pipes spread under the public road in 7 cities of the agglomeration : Grenoble, Échirolles, Eybens, Gières, La Tronche, Pont-de-Claix, Saint-Martin-d’Hères
 - 2nd heating network in France
 - 100 000 housing-equivalent heated (hospital, museums, university, town hall, sport centers and private housing)
 - 118 000 tons of CO₂ avoided (80.1% of renewable and recovery energy)

Case Study

Solution

Definition of the strategy with illustrations

The Grenoble Urban Heating Utility has an existing portfolio of five assets with associated sources of production and is considering its extension to other types of sources to address the fluctuating demand and the environmental constraints. This work aims to address these different aspects. Analytical software is used to assess various scenarios for decarbonizing the network and evaluate their technical, economic, and environmental feasibility. First, we assess the technologies of the heating network in Grenoble. Then, an economic model is developed. We searched in the literature for information regarding the installed power, and then we made hypotheses on the operating time in the year, to compute the energy produced. The cost to produce this energy is

also computed. Then, we model the CO₂ content of the network, depending on how much of each primary source is consumed, and whether this production is made in cogeneration. The CO₂ must be computed considering the life cycle and the direct consumption.

The main goal of this case study is to reach 100% of renewable energies to produce heat for Grenoble's network. Different alternatives can be used to attain this goal. Three different options are studied: the first scenario is to build another plant similar to Biomax, the second scenario is to refurbish all existing plants to use renewable sources rather than the current fossil fuels, and the third scenario is to use new biomass sources, such as walnut shells, as the region is well-known for its production of walnuts. Regarding the active period of the plants, the assumptions made are that all plants are active 50% of the time except the one that burns household waste that is active

all year. All following studies are made compared to the actual situation, meaning a new plant will have new paid workers, while a refurbished plant will have no new workers and therefore no OPEX.

The first option is to build a new plant, very similar to Biomax, the latest plant constructed in Grenoble. When it comes to building a new plant, the decision belongs to the metropolis, and the concessionaire works on the necessary studies. Most of the time, this process is 'bottom-up': the concessionaire presents the idea to the metropolis, and they decide on the investment. The origin of this idea can be linked to a need to develop the renewable energies rate according to the contract. For this scenario, it is considered that all engineering studies have already been carried out.

The second study considers the refurbishment of a plant in use to make it possible to use

renewable sources in these fossil fuel plants. Poterne and Villeneuve are the two plants using the most fossil fuels, mainly coal and gas. Wood pellets are compatible with any coal-burning unit. They are a way to suppress the coal from the mix without huge modifications of the plants, which would be expensive and difficult, depending on the type of equipment used. In this scenario, all the coal will be replaced by wood pellets.

The last scenario focuses on the replacement of fuel oil by walnut shells. Walnut shells are compatible with any wood-burning plant. It is a resource mainly present in Grenoble's area, but the main issue is that the production is very limited. The sector of walnut shells is not developed, there are a lot of small producers, but it is not well-organized. For these reasons, it is not possible to consider a replacement of all fossil fuels by walnut shells. The Grenoble region produces enough walnut to supply the plants and replace fuel oil use.

Identification of the models and methods implemented (mathematical, simulations, etc.)

The modelling framework is based on the literature regarding the installed power, and then includes assumptions on the operating time in the year to compute the energy produced. To compare different scenarios, economic and environmental tools, such as the Net Present Value (NPV) of the project, the levelized cost of energy (LCOE) and of the CO₂ contents of the different networks are used. First, the CAPEX, or initial investment, of each scenario is computed or estimated. This economic indicator is interesting because collectivities tend to invest on less expensive solutions, even if the maintenance costs will be more expensive. Then, the OPEX, or maintenance and operation costs, is computed. It includes wages for the employees and maintenance costs. The benefits for each year are estimated, considering the savings from not paying for fossil fuels but renewable

sources, but also the possible subsidies available for such projects. The benefits from the clients that consume the heat are not considered as each scenario produces the same quantity of heat, and therefore sells the same quantity. The objective here is to compare the scenarios. To know if the project is profitable, the Net Present Value (NPV) is calculated with the formula:

$$NPV = \sum_{t=0}^T \frac{Benefits_t - Costs_t}{(1+r)^t} \quad (6)$$

Where T is the number of years, r is the discount rate, and the correspond to the above benefits and the to the CAPEX for the first year and the OPEX for the following years.

A project will be profitable (and therefore feasible) if the NPV is superior to 0. Then, the Levelized Cost of Energy (LCOE), is computed, to know how much it costs to produce a quantity of heat:

$$LCOE = \frac{\sum_{t=0}^T \frac{Cost_t}{(1+r)^t}}{\sum_{t=0}^T \frac{Energy\ Produced_t}{(1+r)^t}} \quad (7)$$

Where is the energy produced each year.

Finally, the CO₂ content of a network is computed, depending on how much of each primary source is consumed, and whether this production is done through cogeneration. The CO₂ must be computed considering the life cycle and the direct consumption (, as well as emissions avoided thanks to cogeneration. The CO₂ content is the most complex parameter to compute. The methodology of Rossi & Petit (2021) is used. The total CO₂ emissions are given as follows:

$$C = C_{direct} + C_{lca} \quad (8)$$

The direct emissions are computed with:

$$C_{direct} = \frac{q_{CO_2,prod} - q_{CO_2,coge}}{L} \quad (kg_{CO_2}/kWh) \quad (9)$$

where L is the total energy produced over the year, is the quantity of CO₂ emitted by the facilities of production and is quantity of CO₂ saved using cogeneration, simultaneously producing electricity and heat. It is considered that the production of one-kilowatt hour of cogenerated electricity saves 356 g of CO₂ compared to separate production of heat and electricity.

More precisely, is expressed as follow:

$$q_{CO_2,prod} = \sum_i^n E_i \times \alpha_i \times \frac{C_{HCV,i}}{C_{LCV,i}} \quad (10)$$

where is the amount of energy for the input i used for heating, is the direct emissions coefficient that depends on each source, n the amount of sources and is the conversion ratio applicable to the entered quantity for the fuel i (HCV-high calorific value, LCV-low calorific value).

The quantity of CO₂ saved using cogeneration, simultaneously producing electricity and heat is given by the following equation:

$$q_{CO_2,coge} = \sum_i^n P_{e,coge,i} \times 0.365 \quad (11)$$

where $P_{e,coge,i}$ is the electrical power produced thanks to cogeneration. It is estimated that producing 1kWh of electricity through cogeneration avoids the emission of 356g.co₂ compared to separated productions. Then, the life-cycle CO₂ emissions are computed, with

$$C_{lca} = \frac{\sum_i^n E_{ch,i} \times DES_i}{L} + a \quad (kg_{CO_2}/kWh) \quad (12)$$

where DES_i is an environmental coefficient that considers the specific impact of each source, and a a fixed value, corresponding to the operation of the plant and the network.

Identification of the field of implementation (building, industry process, etc.)

Our study is a demonstration of the importance of collaborative projects such as RES4CITY, which bring together various stakeholders, including students, researchers, and industry experts, to work towards a common goal of sustainable development. By combining knowledge, expertise, and resources, it is possible to make significant strides towards creating a more sustainable and equitable future for all. The companies listed below have shown a great interest to the current study, Table 6.

Table 6. Main interested stakeholders

Company	Relevance	Needs & Interests
Grenoble Alpes Metrople	Local Authorities	The lighthouse case will improve their understanding of the system, their interest for a better environmental, and their role in its development and governance.
CCIAG	Heating Company – main local player	
LNCMI Grenoble	National High Magnetic Field Laboratory – different ongoing projects for the electro-intensive installation and opportunities for waste heat recovery into the nearby district heating network	
Tenerdis/AURA-EE	Local energy and environmental hubs already involved in similar projects such as RES-DHC, SDH-p2M	

The study would help them to better understand the economics behind storage and use of waste heat and the networking issues.

Results and Discussion

Table 7 presents the main parameters used in the computations. Some of these values were obtained through interviews, and others were taken from technical reports or in the literature.

Table 7. Main parameters

Average Annual Inflation from 2017 to 2023 (INSEE, 2023)	1.87%
Number of Annual employees on the Biomax site	20
Annual maintenance cost of Biomax Site	1 M€
Cost of a new wood boiler	20 M€
Cost of a new fuel oil boiler	2 M€
a (fixed value, corresponding to the operation of the plant and the network)	4/1000 kgCO ₂ /kWh
Overall efficiency of the Network	80%

For scenario 1, the 2017 CAPEX is discounted with the inflation and used for 2023 CAPEX, and the OPEX is computed with the wages of the annual workers for the plant, the maintenance cost and the wood supply. The operating costs are computed thanks to values found online for the fuel costs. For

scenario 2, the CAPEX is to renovate the coal plant and there is no OPEX because the plants already operate and already have their workers and maintenance. There is a need for investment of 7 Millions euros in order to change the burners because wood doesn't need the same burners as coal. For scenario 3, the CAPEX is to renovate the coal plant and there is no OPEX because the plants already operate and already have their workers and

maintenance. Two different discount rates are used, to model the faster depreciation of fossil fuels compared to wood. Indeed, the price of these energy sources will not vary in the same way. The cost of fossil fuels is more likely to rise rapidly, while the cost of wood will surely increase but slowly. The NPV and payback period are computed with (6) and the CO2 emissions are computed with (7), (8) and (12) and resumed in Table 8.

Table 8. Summary of each scenario

	Notation	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3	Current Situation
CAPEX	CAPEX	61 M€	7 M€	2 M€	/
OPEX	OPEX	1.96 M€	0€	0€	/
NPV (30 years)	NPV	395.5 M€	-112.5 M€	1.65 M€	/
Payback Period	Payback period	12 years	36 years	21 years	/
CO2 direct emissions	Cdirect	-179 gCO2/kWh	-188 gCO2/kWh	-133 gCO2/kWh	-142 gCO2/kWh
CO2 Life-cycle emissions	Clca	23.5 gCO2/kWh	24.2 gCO2/kWh	77.1 gCO2/kWh	78.5 gCO2/kWh
Total CO2 emissions	C	-156 gCO2/kWh	-163 gCO2/kWh	-55.5 gCO2/kWh	-63.1 gCO2/kWh

For the first scenario, the payback period is 12 years, with a discount rate for fossil energies of 5% and of 1% for wood. The values for the discount rate on different sources of energies could have been evaluated a little bit higher but it is the discount rate normalised of the standard discount rate. The investment

discount rate. The investment costs are 61 million of euros (2023) without considering the engineering process (already done for the first site). The cost of wood is increased by 20% to keep a supply coming from the area (around 120 km) and from eco-certified forests.

Figure 14. a) NPV and (b) Energy mix for Scenario 2

As the supply network of walnuts is mainly made of small producers, there is no organization for a re-use of walnut shells. Another option could be to buy full nuts, to separate the shells from the walnut kernel and to sell the kernels. This would be a way to ensure the supply of walnut shells, but a lot of work would be needed on the separation work.

Discussion on Variable Values

More than 40% of the heat produced comes from household waste produced by the inhabitants of Grenoble's area (Grenoble's Urban Heating, 2022). This source is never constant as it directly depends on the inhabitants, but it doesn't vary too much. On the Sinoe website, it is possible to observe variations from 633 thousand tons to 657 thousand tons between 2009 and 2021, but there is no clear increase or decrease. The rate per inhabitant decreased, but there are more and more inhabitants, so the general values do not have too much variation.

The two first scenarios are mainly focused on the use of wood as the main source for this network. The study of the availability of wood in the Grenoble area is necessary to ensure the viability of these projects. Will there be enough wood to supply the network? The Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes region is one of the regions with the most forests (IGN, FCBA, 2019), and the wood stock in this region is the one that experienced the most significant increase between 1976-1994 and 2012-2017. The quantity of forests available is hence sufficient for the supply of the network.

The wood recovered from waste has to be class A or B. Class A wood has never been treated, while Class B wood has been slightly treated with paint or varnish in general. Class C wood is a dangerous waste wood because of their treatment that involves lead paint, preservation products or glue. These chemicals cannot be separated from the wood, so it must be burnt in

very special units. Compared to forest wood, the waste wood has the advantage of being two times less expensive.

Another possibility would be to connect new industrial plants to the network. Some options are studied every 5 years approximately, but the irregularity of these heat sources is often an issue, as a consistent production is better for the network's efficiency. In these cases, an option would be to think of a possible thermal storage solution. Another frequent issue is the temperature needed to heat the water of the network, because in many cases, the temperature reached by the industries is too low to be used with a heat exchanger to heat the network. A portion of the network, that is close to many industrial or research sites, is in study to use low pressure, which would allow industries that produce lower temperature heat to connect to the network.

Regarding the CO₂ content of the network, it includes only the CO₂ emitted by the plants. The

heat recovery unit located in Le Pont-de-Claix emits CO₂ by producing heat during the winter, but these CO₂ emissions are attributed only to the products of the industrial activity, as it is considered that this heat recovered would have been wasted if it were not used in the heat network. Another option would have been to attribute a certain proportion of the CO₂ emission to the heat network, but the CCIAG decided to not take the emissions of the heat recovery unit into the CO₂ content.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The lighthouse case study has presented the heating network in Grenoble, including its stakeholders and the different power plants involved. One originality of this work is regarding the data collection which can be considered as the main challenge to propose

sufficient calculations related to the decarbonisation of the heating network in Grenoble.

The model presented has been applied to three scenarios regarding the use of wood as one main source to the heating network in Grenoble. The results show that among the three scenarios presented, the most realistic would be the second, with 25% of wood pellets and 75% of wood consumption as discussed previously. Indeed, the construction of a new plant is not useful, as this plant would only operate half of the designed time, because of its important capacity. The walnut shell option is interesting for this area but as the industry of walnut shells is not developed, replacing fuel oil by walnut shells does not seem doable, and the low availability of this resource makes it impossible to replace all fossil fuels. However, the use of this material must not be sidelined as its characteristics are interesting.

The objective of the heat network is not to spread further but to reach more people within the network that already exists, i.e. to densify the network. In the end, reaching more people will balance the reduction of consumption, and the heat network will continue to always produce the same amount of heat. Working on a partnership with local producers for bringing an import of walnut shells could be beneficial for Grenoble's heat system. With that, other partnerships could be worked on to bring import of other burning materials for power plants and develop a local economic and energy system.

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